

Neutrosophic RHO –Ideal with Complete Neutrosophic RHO– Ideal in RHO–Algebras

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Abstract: In real-life structures, indeterminacy is always present. Neutrosophic sets theory is a well-known mathematical tool for dealing with indeterminacy. Smarandache proposed the neutrosophic set approach. Neutrosophic sets deal with vague data. In this study, we introduced and investigated several types of ρ –algebra ideals, which we called neutrosophic ρ –subalgebra, complete neutrosophic ρ –subalgebra, neutrosophic ρ –ideal, complete neutrosophic ρ –ideal, neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ –ideal, and complete neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ –ideal, respectively. We also proposed some hypotheses to explain some of the relationships between these ideal types.

Keywords: Neutrosophic ρ –subalgebra; neutrosophic ρ –ideal; neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ –ideal.

1. Introduction

Many different problems in our lives, such as engineering and medical sciences, necessitate uncertainty. Non-classical sets, like fuzzy sets ([19],[24]), soft sets ([25]-[31]), and permutation sets ([32]-[37]) are used to solve some problems in decision making. Smarandache [2] investigates neutrosophic sets as a method for dealing with issues involving unreliable, indeterminate, and persistent data. Imai & Iseki [6] introduce the concepts of BCK –algebra and BCI –algebra. The d –algebra was then introduced by Negger & Kim [9] as a generalization of BCK –algebra. In d –algebra, Negger et al. [8] discussed the ideal theory. In 1965, Zadeh proposed the concept of a fuzzy set [12]. Following that, Atanassov introduced the intuitionistic fuzzy set [1], which is a natural generalization of fuzzy set. Jun et al. [7] later applied the intuitionistic fuzzy set concept to d –algebra. Hasan [4] developed the concept of an intuitionistic fuzzy d –ideal of d –algebra in 2017. After that, Hasan [5] in 2020 introduced the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy d –filter. Smarandache [3] proposed the concept of a neutrosophic set. Next, some basic properties of this notion are studied ([13]-[18]). Also, Smarandache and Rezaei studied the neutrosophic triplet of BI –

algebras[38]. In 2021, some notions of neutrosophic ideals in BCK-algebras are discussed [39].The ρ –algebra was first introduced by Khalil and Abud Alradha[10]. In this paper, we define neutrosophic ρ –subalgebra, complete neutrosophic ρ –subalgebra, neutrosophic ρ –ideal, full neutrosophic ρ –ideal, neutrosophic ρ –ideal, neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ –ideal, and complete neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ –ideal of ρ –algebra, and investigate the relationship between these types.

2. Preliminaries and Some Results.

Here, we will recall basic ideas and results that are necessary in this research.

Definition 2.1.[10] A ρ -algebra is a non-empty set \mathcal{U} with a constant 0 and a binary operation “ ϕ ” satisfying the following axioms:

- (1) $\alpha \phi \alpha = 0$,
- (2) $0 \phi \alpha = 0$,
- (3) $\alpha \phi \beta = 0 = \beta \phi \alpha$ imply that $\alpha = \beta$,
- (4) For all $\alpha \neq \beta \in \mathcal{U} - \{0\}$ imply that $\alpha \phi \beta = \beta \phi \alpha \neq 0$.

Definition 2.2. [10] A non-empty subset Y of a ρ -algebra $(\mathcal{U}, \phi, 0)$ is called ρ - subalgebra of \mathcal{U} if $\alpha \phi \beta \in Y$ for any $\alpha, \beta \in Y$.

Definition 2.3.[10] A non- empty subset Y of a ρ -algebra \mathcal{U} is called an ρ - ideal of \mathcal{U} if satisfies:

- (1) $\alpha, \beta \in Y \Rightarrow \alpha \phi \beta \in Y$,
- (2) $\alpha \phi \beta \in Y \ \& \ \beta \in Y \Rightarrow \alpha \in Y$.

Remark 2.4[10]. If Y is any a ρ - Ideal, then it is easy to show that Y is ρ - subalgebra. However, the convers maybe not true.

Definition2.5.[10] A non- empty subset Y of a ρ -algebra \mathcal{U} is called an $\bar{\rho}$ - ideal of \mathcal{U} if satisfies:

- (1) $0 \in Y$,
- (2) $\alpha \in Y \ \& \ \beta \in \mathcal{U} \Rightarrow \alpha \phi \beta \in Y$.

Proposition 2.6. [10] Let $\emptyset \neq Y \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ where \mathcal{U} is ρ -algebra. Then Y is a ρ - subalgebra of \mathcal{U} if it is $\bar{\rho}$ - Ideal.

Definition 2.7. [2] A Neutrosophic set \mathcal{N} (briefly, NS) over the universal \mathcal{U} is defined by $\mathcal{N} = \{ \langle \alpha, \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \rangle \mid \alpha \in \mathcal{U} \}$, where $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow [0,1]$ are maps, with $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$ and $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$ are real numbers and their values represent the degree of membership, indeterminate and non- membership of α to \mathcal{N} respectively.

Definition 2.8 . [2] A complement neutrosophic set \mathcal{N}^c over the universal \mathcal{U} is defined by

$$\mathcal{N}^c = 1 - \mathcal{N} = 1 - \{ \langle \alpha, \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \rangle \mid \alpha \in \mathcal{U} \} = \{ \langle \alpha, 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \rangle \mid \alpha \in \mathcal{U} \} = \{ \langle \alpha, \mathcal{N}_T^c(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I^c(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F^c(\alpha) \rangle \mid \alpha \in \mathcal{U} \}.$$

Definition 2.9. [2] Let \mathcal{N} be (NS) over the universal \mathcal{U} and $t \in [0,1]$ then the set $\mathcal{N}_t = \{ \alpha \in \mathcal{U} \mid \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \geq t, \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \leq t, \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \geq t \}$ is called neutrosophic set t-cut, (briefly, NS-t-cut).

Definition 2.10. [2] Let $(\mathcal{U}, *, 0)$ be a ρ -algebra and $\mathcal{N} = \{ \langle \alpha, \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \rangle \mid \alpha \in \mathcal{U} \}$ be a neutrosophic set (NS) of \mathcal{U} . We say \mathcal{N} is a neutrosophic ρ -constant of \mathcal{U} if all the maps $\mathcal{N}_T, \mathcal{N}_I, \mathcal{N}_F : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow [0,1]$ are constant maps.

3. Neutrosophic ρ – Subalgebra and Complete Neutrosophic ρ – Subalgebra:

Definition 3.1.A (NS) \mathcal{N} in \mathcal{U} is called a neutrosophic ρ –subalgebra (briefly, NS – ρ – SA) of \mathcal{U} if such that:

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$,
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$,
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$, for any $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$.

Example 3.2. Assume $\mathcal{U} = \{0,1,2,3\}$ is a set and \mathcal{F} is defined by table (1). So, we get $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, 0)$ is a ρ -algebra, We define a (NS) \mathcal{N} in \mathcal{U} as follows:

$$\mathcal{N}_T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.5 & 0.4 & 0.4 & 0.4 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_I = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.2 & 0.3 & 0.3 & 0.3 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_F = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.3 & 0.2 & 0.2 & 0.2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Hence, \mathcal{N} is (NS – ρ – SA).

\mathcal{F}	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	2
2	2	1	0	2
3	3	2	2	0

Table (1) , \mathcal{N} is (NS – ρ – SA)

Lemma 3.3. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS – ρ – SA) of \mathcal{U} then:

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$, (ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$, (iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$, for any $\alpha \in \mathcal{U}$.

Proof: Let \mathcal{N} be (NS – ρ – SA) then

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_T(0) = \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \alpha) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)\} = \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$.
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(0) = \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \alpha) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)\} = \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$.
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(0) = \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \alpha) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)\} = \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$.

Lemma 3.4. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS – ρ – SA) of \mathcal{U} then:

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) \geq \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0)$, (ii) $\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) \leq \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0)$, (iii) $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) \geq \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)$, for any $\alpha \in \mathcal{U}$.

Proof: Let \mathcal{N} be (NS – ρ – SA) , then from lemma (3.3) we obtain: $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$, $\mathcal{N}_F(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$, for any $\alpha \in \mathcal{U}$. Since, $\mathcal{N}^c = 1 - \mathcal{N}$, thus

$$\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \geq 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(0) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0),$$

$$\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \leq 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(0) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0),$$

$$\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \geq 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(0) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0),$$
 This completes proof.

Proposition 3.5: Let \mathcal{N} be (NS) of ρ – algebra $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, 0)$, then \mathcal{N} is (NS – ρ – SA) if

it is $\mathcal{N} = \{ \langle \alpha, \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_T(0), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_I(0), \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_F(0) \rangle \mid \alpha \in \mathcal{U} \}$.

Proof: Let \mathcal{N} be (NS) and $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_T(0), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_I(0), \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$, for any $\alpha \in \mathcal{U}$. Now, Let $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$, then $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = \mathcal{N}_T(0) = \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$, thus $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = \mathcal{N}_I(0) = \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$,

thus $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$,

$\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = \mathcal{N}_F(0) = \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$, thus $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$.

Hence \mathcal{N} is (NS - ρ - SA).

Proposition 3.6. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS) of ρ - algebra $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, 0)$, then \mathcal{N}^c is (NS - ρ - SA).

If $\mathcal{N} = \{ \langle \alpha, \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0) \rangle | \alpha \in \mathcal{U} \}$

Proof: Let $\mathcal{N}^c = \{ \langle \alpha, \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0) \rangle | \alpha \in \mathcal{U} \}$ and let $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$, then $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0) = \min\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\} = \min\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\}$, thus $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\}$, $\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0) = \max\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\} = \max\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\}$, thus $\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\}$, $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0) = \min\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\} = \min\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\}$, thus $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\}$. Hence \mathcal{N}^c is (NS - ρ - SA).

Definition 3.7. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS) of ρ - algebra $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, 0)$, then $K(\mathcal{N}) = \{ \alpha \in \mathcal{U} | \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_T(0), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_I(0) \text{ and } \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_F(0) \}$ is a subset of \mathcal{U} and it is called neutrosophic ρ -kernel of \mathcal{N} over \mathcal{U} .

Example 3.8. Let $\mathcal{U} = \{ a, b, c, d \}$ and define \mathcal{F} on the set \mathcal{U} as table (2). Then $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, a)$ is a ρ -algebra, we define a (NS) \mathcal{N} in \mathcal{U} as follows:

$$\mathcal{N}_T = \begin{pmatrix} a & b & c & d \\ 0.1 & 0.2 & 0.5 & 0.1 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_I = \begin{pmatrix} a & b & c & d \\ 0.1 & 0.3 & 0.4 & 0.1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\mathcal{N}_F = \begin{pmatrix} a & b & c & d \\ 0.1 & 0.3 & 0.5 & 0.1 \end{pmatrix}, K(\mathcal{N}) = \{a, d\}.$$

\mathcal{F}	a	b	c	d
a	a	a	a	a
b	b	a	b	d
c	c	b	a	d
d	d	d	d	a

Table (2), $K(\mathcal{N}) = \{a, d\}$

Proposition 3.9. If \mathcal{N} is (NS - ρ - SA) of $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, 0)$, then $K(\mathcal{N}^c)$ is a (ρ - SA).

Proof: Let $\alpha, \beta \in K(\mathcal{N}^c)$. Then; $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0)$ and $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)$.

Also $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$

$$[\text{since } \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}].$$

$$= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$$

$$= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\}$$

$$= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0),$$

$$\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} [\text{since } \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}].$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \\
 &= \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\} \\
 &= \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \\
 \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \\
 & \quad [\text{since } \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}]. \\
 &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \\
 &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\} \\
 &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0),
 \end{aligned}$$

and from lemma (3.4), W obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) &\geq \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \leq \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \geq \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0) \\
 \text{thus } \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) &= \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0), \\
 \text{this implies } \alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta &\in K(\mathcal{N}^c), \text{ hence } K(\mathcal{N}^c) \text{ is } \rho\text{-subalgebra.}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 3.10. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS - ρ - SA) then \mathcal{N}_t is ρ -subalgebra.

Proof: Assume that \mathcal{N} is (NS - ρ - SA) and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{N}_t$, then

$$(\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \geq t, \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \leq t, \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \geq t) \text{ and } (\mathcal{N}_T(\beta) \geq t, \mathcal{N}_I(\beta) \leq t, \mathcal{N}_F(\beta) \geq t). \text{ Also, } \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \geq t, \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \leq t, \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \geq t, \text{ this implies } \alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta \in \mathcal{N}_t, \text{ hence } \mathcal{N}_t \text{ subalgebra.}$$

Proposition 3.11. Let $(\mathcal{U}, \mathbin{\–}, 0)$ be a ρ -algebra and \mathcal{N} be a (NS) of \mathcal{U} . Then \mathcal{N} is (NS - ρ - SA) if it is neutrosophic ρ -constant.

Proof: Assume that \mathcal{N} is constant. Then for all $\alpha \in \mathcal{U}$, $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_T(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_I(0)$ and $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$, and so $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$ and $\mathcal{N}_F(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$. Next, for all $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$, $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) = \mathcal{N}_T(0) = \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) = \mathcal{N}_I(0) = \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$, $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) = \mathcal{N}_F(0) = \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$, hence \mathcal{N} is (NS - ρ - SA).

Proposition 3.12. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS - ρ - SA). Then $0 \in \mathcal{N}_t$, if $\mathcal{N}_t \neq \emptyset$.

Proof: Assume that \mathcal{N} is (NS - ρ - SA) and $\mathcal{N}_t \neq \emptyset$ then there is at least $\alpha \in \mathcal{N}_t$, also

$$\text{from Lemma (3.3) and Definition (2.9) we obtain, } \mathcal{N}_T(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \geq t, \mathcal{N}_I(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \leq t, \mathcal{N}_F(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \geq t, \text{ this means } 0 \in \mathcal{N}_t.$$

Corollary 3.13. If \mathcal{N} neutrosophic ρ -constant then \mathcal{N}_t is ρ -subalgebra.

Proof: From proposition (3.11) and proposition (3.10).

Definition 3.14. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS) in \mathcal{U} then it is called a complete neutrosophic ρ -subalgebra (briefly, CNS - ρ - SA) of \mathcal{U} if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$,
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$,
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$, for any $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$.

Example 3.15 .Assume $\mathcal{U} = \{0,1,2,3\}$ is a set and ϕ is defined by table (3). So, we get $(\mathcal{U}, \phi, 0)$ is a ρ -algebra, we define a (NS) \mathcal{N} in \mathcal{U} as follows:

$$\mathcal{N}_T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 \\ 0.1 & 0.3 & 0.3 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_I = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 \\ 0.6 & 0.3 & 0.3 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_F = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 \\ 0.2 & 0.4 & 0.4 \end{pmatrix}$$

Hence, \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - SA$).

ϕ	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1
2	2	1	0

Table (3) , \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - SA$)

Lemma 3.16. Let \mathcal{N} be (CNS $-\rho - SA$) of \mathcal{U} then:

(i) $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$, (ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$, (iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$, for any $\alpha \in \mathcal{U}$.

Proof: Let \mathcal{N} be (CNS $-\rho - SA$) then,

(i) $\mathcal{N}_T(0) = \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \phi \alpha) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)\} = \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$.

(ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(0) = \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \phi \alpha) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)\} = \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$.

(iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(0) = \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \phi \alpha) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)\} = \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$. This completes proof.

Proposition 3.17. If \mathcal{N} is a (CNS $-\rho - SA$), then $K(\mathcal{N})$ is $\rho -$ subalgebra.

Proof: Let $\alpha, \beta \in K(\mathcal{N})$, then $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_T(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_T(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_I(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_I(0)$ and

$\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_F(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$. Also, $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \phi \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} = \max\{\mathcal{N}_T(0), \mathcal{N}_T(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_T(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \phi \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} = \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(0), \mathcal{N}_I(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_I(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \phi \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} = \max\{\mathcal{N}_F(0), \mathcal{N}_F(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$, and from lemma (3.16) $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \phi \beta)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \phi \beta)$, $\mathcal{N}_F(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \phi \beta)$, thus $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \phi \beta) = \mathcal{N}_T(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \phi \beta) = \mathcal{N}_I(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \phi \beta) = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$, and $\alpha \phi \beta \in K(\mathcal{N})$ hence $K(\mathcal{N})$ is $\rho -$ subalgebra.

Proposition 3.18. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS) then \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - SA$) if and only if \mathcal{N}^c is (CNS $-\rho - SA$).

Proof: Let \mathcal{N} be (NS $-\rho - SA$) then $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \phi \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \phi \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$, $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \phi \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$, for any $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \phi \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \phi \beta) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \phi \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \phi \beta) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} = \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \phi \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \phi \beta) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\}, \end{aligned}$$

Hence \mathcal{N}^c is (CNS $-\rho - SA$).

Conversely: Let \mathcal{N}^c be (CNS $-\rho - SA$) then $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\}, \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\}, \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\}$, for any $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}, \\ \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \\ \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}, \text{ Hence } \mathcal{N} \text{ is (NS } -\rho - SA). \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.19.

- 1- Let \mathcal{N}^c be is (CNS $-\rho - SA$) then \mathcal{N}_t is $\rho -$ subalgebra.
- 2- Let \mathcal{N} be a neutrosophic ρ -constant then \mathcal{N}_t is $\rho -$ subalgebra.

Proof (1): From Proposition (3.18) and Proposition (3.10).

Proof (2): From Proposition (3.11) and Proposition (3.10).

4. Neutrosophic ρ -Ideal and Complete Neutrosophic ρ -Ideal:

Definition 4.1. Assume $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, 0)$ is a ρ -algebra and \mathcal{N} is (NS) of \mathcal{U} . We say \mathcal{N} is a neutrosophic ρ -ideal of \mathcal{U} (briefly, NS $-\rho - I$) if such that:

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$,
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$,
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$,
- (iv) $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$,
- (v) $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$,
- (vi) $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$, for any $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$.

Example 4.2. Let $\mathcal{U} = \{ \alpha, \gamma, \beta, \delta \}$ be a set with the following table (4), it is clear that $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, \alpha)$ is a ρ -algebra, We define a (NS) \mathcal{N} in \mathcal{U} as follows:

$$\mathcal{N}_T = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & \beta & \gamma & \delta \\ 0.8 & 0.7 & 0.7 & 0.7 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_I = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & \beta & \gamma & \delta \\ 0.4 & 0.6 & 0.6 & 0.6 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_F = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & \beta & \gamma & \delta \\ 0.6 & 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 \end{pmatrix}$$

Hence, \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - I$).

\mathcal{F}	α	β	γ	δ
α	α	α	α	α
β	β	α	β	γ
γ	γ	β	α	γ
δ	δ	γ	γ	α

Table (4): \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - I$).

Lemma 4.3: Every (NS $-\rho - I$) is (NS $-\rho - SA$).

Proof: Let \mathcal{N} be (NS $-\rho - I$). Then from Definition (4.1)-[(i),(ii),(iii)], we get \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - SA$).

Corollary 4.4.

1- Let \mathcal{N} be (NS $-\rho - I$) then \mathcal{N}_t is $\rho -$ subalgebra.

2-Let \mathcal{N} be (NS $-\rho - I$) then \mathcal{N}^c is (CNS $-\rho - SA$).

Proof 1: From Lemma (4.3) and Proposition (3.10).

Proof 2: From Lemma (4.3) and Proposition (3.18).

Lemma 4.5. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS $-\rho - I$) of \mathfrak{U} . Then;

(i) $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$, (ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$, (iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$, for any $\alpha \in \mathfrak{U}$.

Proposition 4.6. If \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - I$), then $K(\mathcal{N})$ is $\rho -$ ideal.

Proof: Let \mathcal{N} be (NS $-\rho - I$) and let $\alpha, \beta \in K(\mathcal{N})$, then $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_T(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_T(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_I(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_I(0)$ and $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_F(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$. Also, $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} = \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(0), \mathcal{N}_T(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_T(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} = \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(0), \mathcal{N}_I(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_I(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} = \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(0), \mathcal{N}_F(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$, and from lemma (4.5) we obtain $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta)$, $\mathcal{N}_F(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta)$. Hence, $\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta \in K(\mathcal{N})$. Now, assume that, $\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta \in K(\mathcal{N})$ & $\beta \in K(\mathcal{N})$ then $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) = \mathcal{N}_T(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) = \mathcal{N}_I(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$, and $\mathcal{N}_T(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_T(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_I(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_F(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$, thus $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} = \mathcal{N}_T(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} = \mathcal{N}_I(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$, and from lemma (4.5) We obtain $\mathcal{N}_T(0) = \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$, $\mathcal{N}_I(0) = \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$, $\mathcal{N}_F(0) = \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$, thus $\alpha \in K(\mathcal{N})$, hence $K(\mathcal{N})$ is $\rho -$ ideal.

Proposition 4.7. If \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - I$), then $K(\mathcal{N}^c)$ is $\rho -$ ideal.

Proof: Let \mathcal{N} be (NS $-\rho - I$) and let $\alpha, \beta \in K(\mathcal{N}^c)$, then

$\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0)$ and $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Also, } \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\} = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0) \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0), \end{aligned}$$

and from lemma (3.4), we obtain

$$\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \geq \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \leq \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathbin{\–}\beta) \geq \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)$$

thus $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)$,
 this implies $\alpha \wp \beta \in K(\mathcal{N}^c)$. Now, let $\alpha \wp \beta, \beta \in K(\mathcal{N}^c)$, then $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) =$
 $\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)$.

And $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)$. Since \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - I$) then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \wp \beta), 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \wp \beta), 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \wp \beta), 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha)\} = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0) \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0), \end{aligned}$$

and from lemma (3.4), we obtain

$$\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) \geq \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) \leq \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) \geq \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)$$

thus $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0)$, $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)$,

this implies $\alpha \in K(\mathcal{N}^c)$, hence $K(\mathcal{N}^c)$ is ρ -ideal.

Proposition 4.8. If \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - I$), then \mathcal{N}_t is ρ -ideal.

Proof: Assume that \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - I$) and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{N}_t$, then $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \wp \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \geq t$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \wp \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \leq t$, $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \wp \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \geq t$, this implies $\alpha \wp \beta \in \mathcal{N}_t$. Now, assume that $\alpha \wp \beta \in \mathcal{N}_t$ & $\beta \in \mathcal{N}_t$, and [since \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - I$)]. We obtain $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \geq t$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \leq t$, $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \geq t$, thus $\alpha \in \mathcal{N}_t$, hence \mathcal{N}_t is ρ -ideal.

Definition 4.9. Assume $(\mathcal{U}, \wp, 0)$ is a ρ -algebra and \mathcal{N} is (NS) of \mathcal{U} . We say \mathcal{N} is a complete neutrosophic ρ -ideal of \mathcal{U} (briefly, CNS- $\rho - I$) if such that:

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \wp \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$,
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \wp \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$,
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \wp \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$,
- (iv) $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$,
- (v) $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$,
- (vi) $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$, for any $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$.

Example 4.10. Let $\mathcal{U} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a set with the following table (5), it is clear that $(\mathcal{U}, \wp, 0)$ is a ρ -algebra, We define a (NS) \mathcal{N} in \mathcal{U} as follows:

$$\mathcal{N}_T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 0.4 & 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_I = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 0.7 & 0.3 & 0.3 & 0.3 & 0.3 \end{pmatrix}, \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}_F = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 0.2 & 0.4 & 0.4 & 0.4 & 0.4 \end{pmatrix}. \text{ Hence, } \mathcal{N} \text{ is (CNS } -\rho - I).$$

f	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	2	4
2	2	1	0	2	2
3	3	2	2	0	3
4	4	4	2	3	0

Table (5): \mathcal{N} is (CNS $-\rho - I$).

Proposition 4.11: Let \mathcal{N} be NS then \mathcal{N} is (NS $-\rho - I$) if and only if \mathcal{N}^c is (CNS $-\rho - I$).

Proof: Let \mathcal{N} be (NS $-\rho - I$), From proof proposition (3.18) we obtain $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\}$, $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$, $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\}$.

$$\text{Now, } \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$$

$$= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$$

$$= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\},$$

$$\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$$

$$= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$$

$$= \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\},$$

$$\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$$

$$= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$$

$$= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\}.$$

Hence \mathcal{N}^c is (CNS $-\rho - I$).

Conversely: Let \mathcal{N}^c be (CNS $-\rho - I$) then from proof proposition, (3.18) we obtain,

$$\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}, \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}, \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}.$$

$$\text{Now, } \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\}$$

$$= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), 1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\}$$

$$= \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\},$$

$$\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\}$$

$$= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), 1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\}$$

$$= \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$$

$$\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\}$$

$$= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), 1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\}$$

$$= \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \wp \beta), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}.$$

Hence \mathcal{N} is (NS – ρ – I)

Corollary 4.12: If \mathcal{N}^c is (CNS – ρ – I). Then;

- 1- \mathcal{N}_t is ρ –subalgebra,
- 2- \mathcal{N}^c is (CNS – ρ – SA),
- 3- \mathcal{N}_t is ρ –ideal.

Proof 1: From proposition (4.11) and corollary (4.4)-1.

Proof 2: From proposition (4.11) and corollary (4.4)-2.

Proof 3: From Proposition (4.11) and Proposition (4.8).

5. Neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ -Ideal and Complete Neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ -Ideal

Definition 5.1. Assume $(\mathcal{U}, \wp, 0)$ is a ρ -algebra and \mathcal{N} is (NS) of \mathcal{U} . We say \mathcal{N} is a neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ -ideal of \mathcal{U} (briefly, NS – $\bar{\rho}$ – I) if such that:

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$,
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$,
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$,
- (iv) $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \wp \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$,
- (v) $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \wp \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$,
- (vi) $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \wp \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$, for any $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$.

Example 5.2. Let $\mathcal{U} = \{x, y, z, w\}$ be a set with the following table(6), it is clear that (\mathcal{U}, \wp, x) is a ρ -algebra. We define a (NS) \mathcal{N} in \mathcal{U} as follows:

$$\mathcal{N}_T = \begin{pmatrix} x & y & z & w \\ 0.6 & 0.4 & 0.4 & 0.4 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_I = \begin{pmatrix} x & y & z & w \\ 0.1 & 0.2 & 0.2 & 0.2 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_F = \begin{pmatrix} x & y & z & w \\ 0.2 & 0.1 & 0.1 & 0.1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence, \mathcal{N} is (NS – $\bar{\rho}$ – I).

\wp	x	y	z	w
x	x	x	x	x
y	y	x	z	w
z	z	z	x	z
w	w	w	z	x

Table (6): \mathcal{N} is (NS – $\bar{\rho}$ – I).

Lemma 5.3. If \mathcal{N} is (NS – $\bar{\rho}$ – I), then \mathcal{N} is (NS – ρ – SA).

Corollary 5.4. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS – $\bar{\rho}$ – I). Then;

- 1- \mathcal{N}_t is ρ –subalgebra,
- 2- \mathcal{N}^c is (CNS – ρ – S).

Proof (1): From lemma (5.3) and proposition (3.10).

Proof (2): From lemma (5.3) and proposition (3.18).

Proposition 5.5. If \mathcal{N} is $(NS - \bar{\rho} - I)$, then \mathcal{N}_t is $\bar{\rho}$ -ideal.

Proof: Assume that \mathcal{N} is $(NS - \bar{\rho} - I)$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{N}_t$, then $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \geq t, \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \leq t, \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \geq t$, this implies $\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta \in \mathcal{N}_t$. Since $[\mathcal{N}$ is $(NS - \bar{\rho} - I)]$, and $\mathcal{N} = \{\alpha \in \mathcal{U} \mid \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \geq t, \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \leq t, \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \geq t\}$. We obtain $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \geq t, \mathcal{N}_I(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \leq t, \mathcal{N}_F(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \geq t$, thus $0 \in \mathcal{N}_t$, hence \mathcal{N}_t is $\bar{\rho}$ -ideal.

Definition 5.6. Assume $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, 0)$ is a ρ -algebra and \mathcal{N} is (NS) of \mathcal{U} . We say \mathcal{N} is a complete neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ -ideal of \mathcal{U} (briefly, $CNS - \bar{\rho} - I$). If such that:

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$,
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}_I(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha)$,
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_F(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$,
- (iv) $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}$,
- (v) $\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\}$,
- (vi) $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}$, for any $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U}$.

Example 5.7. Let $\mathcal{U} = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table(7), it is clear that $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, 0)$ is a ρ -algebra. We define a (NS) \mathcal{N} in \mathcal{U} as follows:

$$\mathcal{N}_T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.4 & 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_I = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.3 & 0.2 & 0.2 & 0.2 \end{pmatrix}, \mathcal{N}_F = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.1 & 0.2 & 0.2 & 0.2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence, \mathcal{N} is $(CNS - \bar{\rho} - I)$.

\mathcal{F}	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2	3
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	3	2	0

Table (7): \mathcal{N} is $(CNS - \bar{\rho} - I)$.

Lemma 5.8. If \mathcal{N} is $(CNS - \bar{\rho} - I)$, then \mathcal{N} is $(CNS - \rho - SA)$.

Proposition 5.9: Let \mathcal{N} be $(CNS - \bar{\rho} - I)$, then $K(\mathcal{N})$ is ρ -subalgebra.

Proof: Assume $\alpha, \beta \in K(\mathcal{N})$, then $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_T(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_T(0), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_I(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_I(0)$ and $\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_F(\beta) = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$. Also, $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} = \max\{\mathcal{N}_T(0), \mathcal{N}_T(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_T(0), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} = \min\{\mathcal{N}_I(0), \mathcal{N}_I(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_I(0), \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} = \max\{\mathcal{N}_F(0), \mathcal{N}_F(0)\} = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$, and $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_I(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta), \mathcal{N}_F(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta)$, thus $\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = \mathcal{N}_T(0), \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = \mathcal{N}_I(0), \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta) = \mathcal{N}_F(0)$, and $\alpha \mathcal{F} \beta \in K(\mathcal{N})$ hence $K(\mathcal{N})$ is ρ -subalgebra.

Proposition 5.10. Let \mathcal{N} be (NS) then \mathcal{N} is $(NS - \bar{\rho} - I)$ if and only if \mathcal{N}^c is $(CNS - \bar{\rho} - I)$.

Proof: Let \mathcal{N} be $(NS - \bar{\rho} - I)$, we obtain $\mathcal{N}_T(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha)$, thus $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha) \geq 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(0) = \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha) \leq 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(0) = \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha) \geq 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(0) = \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \wp \beta) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\}, \\ \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \wp \beta) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} = \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\}, \\ \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \wp \beta) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\} = \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\}, \end{aligned}$$

Hence \mathcal{N}^c is $(\text{CNS} - \bar{\rho} - I)$.

Conversely: Let \mathcal{N}^c be $(\text{CNS} - \bar{\rho} - I)$, then $\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha)$, $\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0) \geq \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha)$, $\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0) \leq \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha)$, $\mathcal{N}_T(0) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(0) \geq 1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha)$,

$$\mathcal{N}_I(0) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(0) \leq 1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha),$$

$$\mathcal{N}_F(0) = 1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(0) \geq 1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha) = \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha),$$

and from the following

$$\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\}, \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) \geq \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\},$$

$$\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) \leq \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\}, \text{ for any } \alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{U},$$

We obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_T(\alpha \wp \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_{T^c}(\beta)\} = \min\{\mathcal{N}_T(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_T(\beta)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_I(\alpha \wp \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) \leq 1 - \min\{\mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_{I^c}(\beta)\} = \max\{\mathcal{N}_I(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_I(\beta)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}_F(\alpha \wp \beta) &= 1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha \wp \beta) \geq 1 - \max\{\mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\alpha), 1 - \mathcal{N}_{F^c}(\beta)\} = \min\{\mathcal{N}_F(\alpha), \mathcal{N}_F(\beta)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence \mathcal{N} is $(\text{NS} - \bar{\rho} - I)$.

Corollary 5.11. If \mathcal{N}^c is $(\text{CNS} - \bar{\rho} - I)$. Then;

- 1- \mathcal{N}_t is ρ -subalgebra,
- 2- \mathcal{N}^c is $(\text{CNS} - \rho - SA)$,
- 3- \mathcal{N}_t is $\bar{\rho}$ -ideal.

Proof 1: From proposition (5.10) and corollary (5.4)-1.

Proof 2: From Proposition (5.10) and Corollary (5.4)-2.

Proof 3: From Proposition (5.10) and Proposition (5.5).

6. Conclusion

We presented and examined several kinds of ρ -algebra ideals in this research, which we called neutrosophic ρ -subalgebra, complete neutrosophic ρ -subalgebra, neutrosophic ρ -ideal, complete neutrosophic ρ -ideal, neutrosophic ρ -ideal, neutrosophic ρ -ideal, neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ -ideal, and complete neutrosophic $\bar{\rho}$ -ideal, respectively. We also suggested some theories try to explain some of these ideal type relationships. In future work, we will use soft set theory to study our notions and results in neutrosophic soft sets.

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